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Developing the formal SME sector in South Africa: is policy helping?

Ms Pitsi Mnisi, Doctoral Researcher, Heriot-Watt University

Prof Laura Galloway, Professor, Heriot-Watt University

Dame Prof Heather McGregor, Provost, Heriot-Watt University

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Executive summary

Research on entrepreneurship in sub-Saharan Africa tends to focus on survivalism and the informal sector. In many cases this research engages with the experiences and outcomes of policies and programmes designed to mitigate institutional gaps and conditions of resource deficiency for these informal and often precarious enterprises. South Africa, as the second largest African economy after Nigeria, is no exception to this. Alternatively, however, little is known about the experiences of entrepreneurs in the formal sector and the effects of policies on them. This research engages with this, finding that while policies may be intended to mitigate some of the environmental challenges for South African entrepreneurs, in fact, implementation inefficiencies stymie the utility of much of the support formal businesses might receive.

The South African environment for SMEs

There is a strong rationale for policy-makers to support business activities, and in turn, to support this, there are implications for researchers seeking to inform policy. There is a growing body of knowledge about issues and challenges as they are experienced by entrepreneurs in sub-Saharan African nations. Incomplete institutions, gaps in provision, mismanagement, corruption, lack of profile are only some of the issues that have been identified (eg., BASA, 2025; Ukanwa, et al. 2022; Moleketi, 2009).

Consequently, our knowledge has developed to include that, for example, informal institutions are often used to mitigate a lack of formal institutional support, such as robust education, training and finance sectors (Viswanathan, et al. 2014; Galloway, et al. 2023), and that engagement of government and external policies and programmes to support informal entrepreneurship have resulted in outcomes that are largely found to be inconsistent (CCSA, 2023). Given that research focus is almost exclusively informal entrepreneurship, however, there

is little understanding of how formal enterprises operate in the institutional sub-Saharan context. To this end, we developed a study of established firms in the formal sector in South Africa, to explore their experiences.

Specifically, formal South African SMEs ranging from five to 16 years old were purposefully sampled from sectors including mining, business services, manufacturing and personal services. Using a qualitative methodology, primarily grounded in interviews, we asked these entrepreneurs what they considered to be the issues they were experiencing within South Africa's institutional environment, and what they would like to see to help their mitigation. While the research was framed by neo-institutional theory and by engaging with agency theory in terms of exploring how these entrepreneurs navigate the operating environment, in this short piece, we focus on the practical and policy-relevant outcomes of the research.

Intentions versus implementation

The research shows a disjoint between the intentions of government policies and programmes and the lived realities of businesses in the formal sector in South Africa. For example, throughout interviews, respondents referred to DFIs as being as restrictive as banks in terms of conditionality for lending – even if the costs of loans are reduced, access to these loans still requires collateral, and it is collateral that is the key barrier to access. Similarly, in terms of adherence to BEE, there is broad reportage that the inclusion intentions are largely ineffective.

The key issue emerging from this research is a lack of monitoring of implementation of programmes such as DFIs and BEE; a discord between policy rhetoric and engagement. With little or no accountability required, policy and other support mechanisms are unlikely to achieve their aspirational goals. The entrepreneurs included in this research noted how this would be reasonably simple to change, and both penalties and incentivization, such as tax breaks, were suggested as means by which implementation effectiveness could be managed.

Policy and practice recommendations

There is huge potential within the formal business sector in South Africa for return for government in social and economic terms; indeed, SMEs are advocated to be one of South Africa's greatest potentials for generating growth in employment, GDP and reducing inequalities (SACCI, 2025). To realise this potential, the following are critical:

1. Policies on integration and equality cannot achieve their intentions unless they are accompanied by meaningful strategies of implementation. These might include:
 - Tax or other fiscal incentives for policy-advocated inclusivity
 - Penalties, financial or fiscal, for non-adherence to inclusivity policies
 - Policy targets included in both government and companies' strategies objectives, and inclusion as key performance indicators of management.
2. Linked to the above, a means by which organisations may report and be accountable to their adherence to policies is required.

3. In terms of access to financial resources, soft loans can only go so far. It is not sufficient to offer better-than-market services such as lower interest rates if the conditionality for accessing these does not vary significantly from mainstream and market lenders. Where there is no clear distinction in terms of conditionality, these will only provide cheaper service to those firms that already can achieve compliance.
4. Given that access to financial support products and services is the key barrier to their use, support programmes that seek to improve access should be clearly distinct from market services in terms of their conditionality. In particular, alternatives to the requirements of security and/or collateral should be explored.
5. Rather than replicate support for SMEs elsewhere, South Africa should pursue innovative solutions to engage and support the SME sector and these should be cognizant of the highly contextualized environment in which they are operating.

To conclude, integration, mitigation of generations of discrimination, and empowerment of the population to increase their aspirations and their fortunes aside, the formal sector in South Africa is high value, with the potential for enormous growth and opportunity exploitation. One of the largest economies in Africa, with good access to education and skills development, and an increasingly diversified sectoral landscape, the environment is well-placed for entrepreneurship and innovation to thrive. Yet the current policy approach is still perceived as benefiting the few, those with good levels of capital (social, financial and otherwise), rather than encouraging a broader entrepreneurial ecosystem to emerge.

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